

In your opinion, what are the biggest barriers for students when it comes to meaningful SA?

1. Poor understanding of some of the learning outcomes (ethics in particular).
2. Not seeing ways in which they can connect what they are doing already to SaA (e.g. learning a new language to better communicate with an aunt). This leads to a lot of activities with less personal impact (like cleaning the park)

Planning I guess, students often ask me last minute to be their supervisor for a thing after which I want to see proof that they've done it, they tell me they'll update MB and get back to me and I never hear from them again...

Most are stuck in the frame of mind there is no link to education - many overlook the developmental progress that supports academic growth and beyond.

I'm sorry, I don't know about SA; only CAS.

their own initiative. They have a hard time generating ideas.

Another hoop the IB expects students to jump through

They want it to be easy, not a lot of extra work

Language barriers can impact students being a part of supporting their community in this non-English speaking country.

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Can you describe one way you *could* integrate an SA opportunity into your subject teaching?

One unit I have is on News and the lack of positive news. I have encouraged students to share positive news (via social media) or outlets within the school.

Another unit is on the tales of xxx the spider and the history of xxx slavery. This is timed around Keti Koti (the independence of Suriname). Students can take this to spread awareness and visit Keti Koti festivities as well.

I also have units simply on the country, with ways to partake in the country's society. Students could join a sports club or other club as a means to challenge themselves.

All of these options are mentioned explicitly throughout the unit.

Language B is kind of difficult to integrate SA with I feel. Sure I can discuss any topic because it's all language but aside from teaching others their own native language or something I can't think of much.

We already do this by taking assignments we do (think: Informing brochures on cancer, STIs) and together discovering how you could take that one step further - analysing a diet, and then challenging students to also look at if they could take that into their next few months and change their eating habits; recon into a fitting type of sports; ..

I guess it's similar to CAS in the DP?

design is about problem solving and initiating ideas, so this is easy: design a bird house to support the birds in the neighborhood. science: anatomy of sport: picking up a new sports. etc.

NVT

Let them come up with ideas

I would love to incorporate more SA through sustainable initiatives in the community, through both English and Theatre.

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What support would you need to do this effectively (e.g., planning time, collaboration, examples)?

I don't think I would need any.

Examples would be most helpful. Time I already have very little of I feel.

A bit more SG time, to together recon and brainstorm - to fill in ideas for each unit.

Maybe a broad introduction to SA in the MYP; I don't really know much about it and don't refer to it in class.

id love more examples per level. is MUN an SaA?

SA day/week. Connecting with the wider community -

planning time

I would love more examples on how to do this.

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